

SEARCHING AND STRUCTURING THE TWITTER STREAM FOR CRISIS RESPONSE: A FLEXIBLE CONCEPT TO SUPPORT RESEARCH AND PRACTICE

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Abstract

In the context of crisis situations, the high information value of Twitter has already been demonstrated in several studies. However, there are various issues that prevent users from deploying information from social media in practice. This paper outlines the experiences and results of the Data4Human project. In collaboration with the World Food Programme, the German Red Cross and the Humanitarian Open Street Map Team, requirements were defined that have to be fulfilled for a practical use of the data. On this basis, a modular processing system was developed which, in combination with a dashboard, enables the practitioners to evaluate the data and analysis results in a structured and interactive manner. Pre-trained and adjustable machine learning methods combined with search- and unsupervised aggregation-capabilities allow to yield different thematic views on the data. By using two use cases, Cyclone Idai and Kenneth in 2019 in Southern Africa and the current war in Ukraine, it becomes apparent, that interactive and customizable methods are of great importance, as well as an effective data representation that enables the identification of relevant content. Based on the results obtained and the user feedback received, future research guidelines are defined in order to close the evident gap between research and practice.

INTRODUCTION

Crisis informatics research from the past two decades impressively demonstrates the potential of social media data as a valuable information source for various crisis management applications [1]. Studies on social media usage and communication patterns [2], public information and warning [3], event/topic detection and tracking [4], situational awareness [5], disaster preparedness [6] and resilience [7], and decision-making [8] cover the complete disaster cycle. However, issues like data retrieval, information overload, limited representativity of data, location uncertainties, and unknown trustworthiness along with privacy and ethical concerns, still hamper the exploitation of social media data in practice.

With special emphasis on crisis and emergency response, the German Aerospace Center (DLR) project Data4Human (D4H) [9], among others, addresses the question of how social media can be utilized in practice. The goal is to enable our partners World Food Programme (WFP), German Red Cross (GRC), and the Humanitarian Open Street Map Team (HOTOSM) to gain additional local insights and information, for example regarding (sub) events as well as impacts

on population and infrastructure. Twitter data analysis for cyclones Idai and Kenneth (Mozambique, 2019) as well as for the war in Ukraine immediately made clear that potential thematic questions can change rapidly over time and are often not even known in advance, as they may arise from the content of the data itself. Purposeful yet flexible search mechanisms to robustly identify and aggregate relevant information, along with sophisticated information management, can help to address the aforementioned shortcomings and therefore, play an extraordinary role for application-oriented crisis informatics research.

In this paper, the evident gap between research and emergency management practice is addressed. Based on our findings and experiences within the D4H project, we outline general guidelines that we are convinced will help to tailor future social media research for practical applications. Our proposed prototype for Twitter data acquisition, analysis and interactive information access is designed according to these findings and is iteratively shared with and evaluated by our partners during the development. The use case of bi-directional validation of information candidates from multiple sources appears to be our first step towards a contribution of Twitter information to existing emergency response workflows.

In the following section, the scientific literature is introduced. Then, different humanitarian frameworks as well as the requirements defined by the practitioners involved in D4H are presented. Thereafter, a prototype of a modular workflow and data visualization is presented and finally discussed based on the two use cases and with respect to the specified requirements.

RELATED WORK

A primary function of social media during a crisis response is to improve situational awareness [3, 8]. According to Endsley's model [10], situational awareness is defined as: "the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning, and the projection of their status in the near future". Based on this perception, decisions are taken and actions are executed.

Within the process of gaining situational awareness through local information, the actual question at hand and the definition of relevance appears to be role dependent. Therefore, interactivity and the customization of social media filtering and analysis algorithms turn out to be essential [11, 12]. In contrast, the identification or classification of informative [13], crisis-related [14] or actionable [15] tweets is commonly approached with pre-trained machine

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learning models [16], often focusing on specific pre-defined event types, like landslides [17] or floods [18, 19], or on specific topics, like injured or dead people [5] and eyewitness reports [20].

With emphasis on rather generic applications, several comprehensive monitoring systems comprising a collection of analysis methods and functionalities have been proposed. Examples are EAIMS [21] for real-time detection of emergency events, related information finding and credibility analysis, and Event Tracker [22] providing a unified view of an event, integrating information from news sources, emergency response officers, social media, and volunteers. However, only few studies are available, in which Twitter analysis methods proposed by researchers have been evaluated by practitioners. Promising results obtained with a visualization framework for situational awareness [23] and a real-time system for detecting landslide reports on social media [17] underpin the need for flexible systems comprising different methods of data analysis and interactive information access.

Finally, only a few studies examine the integration of social media data into emergency management processes. They emphasize the importance of geolocation as well as search and filtering functionalities [24]. Nevertheless, interactive "dashboards have received trivial attention in terms of the usable representation of such information" [25]. Therefore, little is known about the role social media can play in the decision-making processes. It's a causality dilemma as, on the one hand, crisis management does not know what to expect from social media data, and on the other hand, scientists do not know existing workflows and issues that come up during a mission. For these reasons, it is important to work closely with the practitioners and provide them with flexible tools that allow them to access and explore the data based on varying information needs and to evaluate the potential for their purposes.

USER REQUIREMENTS

In the course of a crisis, each practitioner is confronted with a variety of tasks and questions that may change rapidly depending on the type of crisis or its development. For example, the analysis framework of the International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (IFRC) focuses on three analytical pillars covering crisis impact, severity of conditions and gaps in crisis response. For this purpose, information is needed covering, for example, the potential driver of the crisis, damages & losses, physical & mental well-being, or availability of supplies & services [26]. Beyond this "big picture", local relief forces need information on "implicit and explicit requests related to emergency needs that should be fulfilled or serviced as soon as possible" [27]. In comparison, WFP focuses on aspects of food security and analyzes, for example, agro-economical conditions, as well as political and socio-economic factors to quantify their impact on food intake and health status of individuals [28]. Hence, interactivity and the customization of social media

filtering and analysis algorithms are essential for improving situational awareness [11, 12].

More specifically, the D4H practitioners highlighted six requirements addressing the data, information extraction, the processing pipeline and the visualization of the results.

(1) Quick & continuous data availability: As additional data source, social media unfolds its potential when relief workers cannot be on site and therefore no first-hand information is available. In most cases, this is especially true at the beginning of a crisis or in cut-off places to which relief workers cannot gain access. If data meets this requirement, it is possible to bridge existing information gaps, for example, between the acquisition of satellite images.

(2) Location is key: In order to capture the extent and severity of affected areas, geospatial information - including uncertainty information - is crucial. Again, especially at the beginning of a crisis, such data can help to organize relief workers and mapping efforts.

(3) Globally applicable workflow: To be able to operate in numerous countries, the workflow should function independently of the respective language and should be scalable to highly different amounts of data volumes.

(4) Flexible methods: Since each organizations has its own thematic focus and each situation can change, the question at hand can vary quickly. Hence, the tools should ideally be applicable to different scenarios such like hurricanes, droughts, armed conflicts, or social domino effects resulting from a crisis. The flexibility and the social component in particular, offers the possibility to proactively identify threatening situations in advance in order to avert the crisis or lessen its effects.

(5) Data bias & trustworthiness: Only a small fraction of affected people post online. It must be made clear if certain areas and certain population groups are not well represented in the data. Moreover, information obtained from a single tweet is not trusted.

(6) Visualization: On the one hand, the visualization should capture the big picture so that context is given and a summary is provided for a quick understanding of the situation. On the other hand, detailed information such as precise coordinates, media, or urgent requests should provide a foundation for immediate actions. In addition, the platform should be user-friendly and operable without technical and methodological background in Geographic Information Systems (GIS) or Natural Language Processing (NLP).

MODULAR PROCESSING SYSTEM

The concept of the resulting modular processing system includes a framework of loosely assembled modules ranging from data acquisition to pre-processing, as well as information extraction, classification and verification. The concept allows to add modules, to adapt them individually to the respective user, or to update modules to the current state of research. In combination with data representation via a dashboard, the concept offers the possibility to involve the practitioners through feedback loops. This enables our users

to gain own insights and learn what types of information is hidden in the data. According to their evaluations, further requirements and questions for the scientific work unfold. The initial prototype (Fig. 1) includes:

Data Acquisition The respective user can trigger the processing pipeline by defining an area of interest. Thus, location specific queries can be directed to Twitter’s live endpoint or full archive endpoint. In turn, georeferenced tweets and its media can be retrieved continuously, contributing to fulfill requirement (1) and (2).

Translation Translators like Google Translate offer a large portfolio of more than 100 languages [29]. Semantic subtleties may be lost, but by translating into English, various modules can be added to the workflow that are primarily designed for English language, such as for named entity recognition (NER) or sentiment analysis. Therefore, modules can be used flexibly and almost worldwide, addressing requirement (3). Moreover, a translation allows consistent interpretation of the tweet content by the user.

Text pre-processing & Text Embedding A usual pre-processing is performed, including the replacement of URLs, hashtags, mentions, emojis or character repetitions, as well as removing spaces or line breaks. After this cleanup, only tweets with at least three words are forwarded and transformed into an 512-dimensional Universal Sentence Encoder [30] embedding, which is performing well for supervised and unsupervised classification tasks [31, 32].

Supervised Classification To identify crisis-related tweets, a deep neural network was trained and tested (F1-Score 0.90) based on the HumAid data set [33]. Based on this pre-trained model, a separation into relevant and non-relevant content can be made. Furthermore, the same data set was used to train a second deep neural network to classify tweets into 10 different humanitarian categories like *infrastructure & utility damage, injured or dead people* or *requests or urgent needs*. In order to meet requirement (4), this data set was selected in agreement with the practitioners, as it is specifically designed to interpret humanitarian aid-related information from different types of disasters [33] and comes closest to the practitioners’ own framework.

Named Entity Recognition As a last processing step, entities are extracted from each tweet text. Persons, organizations, and miscellaneous tokens are obtained by using Flair [34]. In addition, GazPNE2 [35] is used for a reliable identification of place names. In comparison to other approaches, GazPNE2 achieves state-of-the-art results (F1-Score: 0.8). So far, identified entities serve as a basis for summaries as demanded in requirement (6).

Database Along with the initial tweet information retrieved from the Twitter API, its translation, stopwords, embedding, the classification results and named entities get

Figure 1: Modular processing system

Figure 2: Dashboard design and structure

stored in a geospatial database which can be updated on a regular basis.

DATA VISUALIZATION

The user is given access to the database with the help of a dashboard. Its functionality supports the user in browsing through the data and directs him to potentially relevant topics. Furthermore, it offers the possibility to specify self-defined queries to find out whether and which information is available under consideration of a particular topic (requirement 4). Therefore, the dashboard offers a total of six different

containers. Container 1 can be used to filter the database based on keywords and time, but also based on various features resulting from the processing pipeline, like relevance score and humanitarian categories. This selection is then forwarded to container 2, where the geographical distribution of the tweets is displayed as a heat map including point and bounding boxes features. Based on this geographical overview, the user can specify a region of interest.

Tweets originating from a specific area are then forwarded for detailed content analysis to container 3. Based on the sentence embedding, tweets get clustered by a Chinese Restaurant Process clustering approach [36] and then visualized by using UMAP [37] as dimension reduction technique. The user can interactively specify the cosine similarity threshold, which decides about the cluster assignments. In the background of this interactive clustering process, place names and other named entities are summarized, and the term frequency-inverse document frequency (tf-idf) is calculated for each cluster. Those cluster summaries as well as individual tweet information such as text, its translation and time stamp are shown to the user in container 4 when hovering over the data points. In combination with the summary, the clustering structures the feature space and provides a quick overview of the data. In addition, it is possible to refine the query by the *request or urgent needs* category to identify circumstances that require a rapid response (requirement 6). In addition, semantic clustering of tweets can be used to place individual information in context. Together with the visualization of the temporal development of a cluster and its media in container 5 and 6, additional indicators for the verification are provided to increase trustworthiness (requirement 5). Finally, a user can export a selection of tweets for further analysis.

PRACTICAL USE CASES

The case of Cyclone Idai and Kenneth was chosen because it is considered as one of the most severe natural disasters in South Africa, with which the practitioners are already familiar. The database obtained from Twitter’s full archive endpoint contains 82,482 tweets, that were posted within Malawi, Zimbabwe or Mozambique between 15/03/2019 and 26/04/2019. Although these countries do not produce a high tweet volume and the number of relevant tweets is low (~150/day), it is possible to get an impression of the crisis over time.

For example, tweets of the *request and urgent need* category indicate the difficult supply situation of the affected population, especially of children and elderly, a cholera outbreak, as well as warnings about gender-based violence or human trafficking. The category *rescue volunteering & donation efforts* is holding not only calls for donations, but also a small discussion about Zimbabwe’s political party in charge, allegations of corruption and rumors about the theft of donated relief supplies. Based on this thematic overview, more precise keyword-based queries provide more insight into topics, such as efforts undertaken by organizations to

Table 1: Selection of tweets reporting about hospitals

'Russian invasion: hospital attacked in Balakleya: "Russian troops fired on a hospital in Balakleya, Kharkiv region, which they occupied. 70 medics and patients have to be evacuated.'
'Mariupol. Direct strike of Russian troops at the maternity hospital. Atrocity! How much longer will the world be an accomplice ignoring terror? People and children are under the wreckage. #SafeAirliftUkraine'
'Here I am with two of the five medical doctors who remain in Zolochiv, which is located in the far north of #Ukraine, (about 10 miles from Russia), after being given the okay to come up from the hospital’s bomb shelter after today’s artillery attack on us.#StandWithUkraine'
'#RussianOccupants completely destroyed city center and hospital in #Izium, #Kharkiv region #Ukraine'

contain the cholera outbreak, including vaccinations and provision of drinking water. Nevertheless, compared to the scale of the crisis, which affected millions of people, the density of information is quite low.

With the beginning of the Russian invasion in Ukraine, the question arose whether the tool could unveil information from Twitter to support a practitioner’s project collecting and reviewing secondary data. In the course of the Ukraine war, the database has been regularly updated since the beginning of the invasion on 20/02/2022 until 18/05/2022 and includes 301,792 tweets.

Especially the categories *infrastructure & utility damage, displaced people & evacuations* or *injured dead people* offer a wide range of local information. Particularly noticeable are detailed reports about the medical infrastructure. After being guided to that topic, a "hospital" - keyword query reveals reports as exemplified in Table 1.

According to the practitioners, this information is of value because, due to the complex course of the war, only sparse and sometimes contradictory information on the state of hospitals is available. In this regard, tweets can serve as an indicator revealing valuable and timely insights. Using the dashboard, hospital related information can be identified and exported for further analysis, enabling a comparison with other secondary data sources as well as internal reports from the practitioners.

Since location is key, it is noteworthy that the majority of tweets (~95%) are geolocated by a bounding box, which in the case of the Ukraine, spans around the entire country. Therefore, 526 hospital related tweets were extracted containing an extracted place name, which could be allocated to 48 different cities belonging to 17 different oblasts. Regardless of the course of individual events, the database contains information on 25 different cities where attacks on hospitals were reported. Furthermore, 33 cities were reported to have functioning or partially operating hospitals, and nine cities were reported where hospitals are completely destroyed. As often only city names are mentioned in the tweets and hospi-

tal names are missing, exact identification is not possible in most cases. Moreover, nearly 50% of the tweets report on the same event over a longer period of time, without introducing additional information.

As this practical demonstration shows, the initial prototype provides a first flexible toolkit that allow the practitioners to access the data, examine it according to different perspectives, and cross-check these findings with further data sources. Nevertheless, the potential of Twitter is highly dependent on the country and the virality of certain topics.

DISCUSSION

From the promising results of the current prototype, further guidelines are discussed in the following in order to direct future research to better meet the user requirements.

To flexibly adapt the modular system to a respective practitioner (requirement 4), a close cooperation is required. Several organizations have their own innovation teams and even databases containing documents and reports organized according to their respective framework. This provides a foundation to adapt especially the pre-trained supervised modules intended for overload reduction and categorization, to the practitioner's framework. However, to keep the customization effort low, it is important to evaluate the application of methods optimizing the labeling and training process, such as few shot models, one-class models, or model-assisted labeling [38] [39].

Subsequent to information discovery, information representation plays an important role (requirement 6), that is scarcely investigated so far. To further improve the usability, standards addressing data structure and its representation should be defined together with the practitioners. According to the practitioners' feedback, grouping and contextualization of selected content by interactive clustering already provides a solid overview. Moreover, it should be iterated how meaningful summaries can be extracted from a data selection, capturing most important and relevant information that are further optimized for the practitioner's internal communication.

Since location is key (requirement 2), the coarse resolution of Twitter's geolocation is noteworthy. A large part of the investigated tweets refers to the country level. Therefore, further implementations and future research on place name extraction and disambiguation are fundamentally important to correctly identify the place and thus to capture the extent and development of a crisis as precisely as possible. The Ukrainian use case shows that localization at least on city level is feasible for Twitter data.

The ability to extract and locate place names also offers the advantage of synergistically integrating multiple data sources. Text-based data, such as documents, reports, news or blogs can be used to derive further information while also enabling cross-validation of information, increasing trust (requirement 5). In addition, the synergistic use of GIS data such as satellite imagery, administrative statistics or Open Street Map can be used to identify areas and populations

that may be underrepresented by web data (requirement 5) or to link critical infrastructure. Therefore, social media has to be considered as an additional data source of information, which stands out due to its fast and easy data availability.

By integrating multiple data sources, overload reduction and information management in particular become more important. Furthermore, challenges arise with regard to the thematic linking of different data sources, the spatial linking due to different resolutions and with regard to a consistent data acquisition for global applicability (requirement 3). Hence, more collaborative research on how to tailor and systematically fuse social media analysis and other data sources is required.

CONCLUSION

This paper introduces a modular processing pipeline and interactive data visualization tool which was iteratively developed together with DRK, WFP and HOTOSM enabling the practitioners to explore the potential of Twitter data to enhance situational awareness under consideration of varying information needs and requirements. The two use cases demonstrated the potential of the prototype and provided further guidance for future implementations and research.

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